

National
Oceanography
Centre

Multi-mode sensor dashboards

**Conceptual framework to enhance the research
impact of National Oceanography Centre (NOC)
sensor data through end-user applications**

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ENHANCING NOC RESEARCH IMPACT

Sensors are everywhere. New sensor technologies, like Internet of Things, are already advancing National Oceanography Centre (NOC) science. As these types of technologies evolve, sensors will become even more significant in our marine research. Common digital infrastructure will be needed to effectively enhance the research impact from NOC sensor data. Through internal NOC RISC support, we studied how this could be achieved through end-user applications. Following requirement gathering sessions and software demonstrations, this report describes a conceptual data-staging framework in support of end-user applications and data-driven discovery.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

As part of the RISC Multi-mode Sensor Dashboards project, we carried out requirement gathering sessions with participants from across NOC to understand how we can improve the research impact of NOC sensor data through end-user applicationsⁱ. These sessions highlighted that an underlying data staging framework for sensor data would be essential. However, separate groups from across NOC will have established separate ways to receive, collate and even share data from sensors according to their preferred practices. Finding common ground between the established pools of sensor data and end-user applications will be needed. Using the principles of Grossman (2018)ⁱⁱ, the research impact from end-user applications could be enhanced using an end-to-end,

“Frameworks need to be devised that leverage interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration which support creative solutions and engagement with communities.”

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF SENSORS FOR OUR ENVIRONMENT

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data commons-like approach (Figure 1). A *data commons* is typically a cloud-based software platform with a governance structure that allows a community (in our case NOC and its collaborators) to manage, analyse and share its data. In this concept, a minimum set of static services are developed into a narrow middle architecture (Data Commons framework), enabling a light-weight core of data organisation, harmonisation and machine access points. The importing, curation and integration services for getting data into the *commons* (one “end”) and the data exploration, analysis and collaboration services for getting knowledge and impact out of the *commons* (the other “end”) are more flexible and are the focus of different competing and innovative efforts until the community begins to recognise and adopt approaches that seem to be most effective. Essentially, these “ends” become sets of commonly used NOC services and tools that help bridge the gap between different data sources and the needs of

different end-user applications. *Data commons* have shown to be successful collaborative platforms. The Google Data Commonsⁱⁱⁱ has successfully integrated economic, social and environmental data into interactive graphs. As part of the project, we delivered a roadmap to develop impact from NOC sensor data and end-user applications^{iv}. Our aim will be to initially focus on small data volume, high research impact NOC sensor demonstrators to establish a core *commons* framework, governance structure and emerging 'ends' with specific use cases. We will then build resilience and evolve our 'ends' towards an operational set of commonly used services with further advanced use cases.

A YouTube video providing further information about the RISC Multi-Mode Sensor Dashboards project is available^v.

KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

(1) Use cloud-native software

Build highly scalable, flexible, and resilient applications that can be updated quickly (with limited downtime) to meet evolving stakeholder demands, data volumes and high availability of services.

(2) Minimise commercial data egress costs

Limit the costs associated with data egress by potentially using private clouds for data storage; where data transactions within the commons are needed; or for frequently downloaded datasets.

(3) Involve the community

Community-driven, created by many diverse groups from across NOC (One NOC) as well as external collaborators to foster a diversity of ideas and enhance research impact.

(4) Provision for promotion

Provide promotional support, training, and tools to enhance the impact of applications. For example, in educational resources and policy making.

(5) Provide an asset register

Create an asset register that will enable end-users to discover apps, tools, and services (as well as datasets).

(6) Develop an impact case

Develop and record evaluation and monitoring metrics to support the research impact and overall case of the digital framework.

(7) Low barriers to entry

The 'rules of engagement' are defined to enable easy uptake of the system. For example, FAIR data requirements are maintained as low as possible, with data providers being encouraged to gradually increase the information they provide over time through training and support.

Figure 1. End-to-end narrow middle architecture approach based on Grossman (2018) that enables the framework to work with existing NOC sensor networks, NOC business tools and generate data-driven impact through user applications.

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- ⁱ https://zenodo.org/records/13885882/files/multiModeApps_Requirements.jpg?download=1
 - ⁱⁱ <https://medium.com/@rgrossman1/a-proposed-end-to-end-principle-for-data-commons-5872f2fa8a47>
 - ⁱⁱⁱ <https://datacommons.org/>
 - ^{iv} https://zenodo.org/records/13885882/files/multiModeApps_RoadMap.pdf?download=1
 - ^v <https://youtu.be/6uuKWwOlw8>

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